

The Impact of Loads on the Body of Women in the Field of Physical Education and Sports

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Abstract:

In the article, the participation of women in physical education and sports activities and their role in the development of society, their structure and content, the system of competition activities are studied.

Keywords: young athletes, training program, planning, distribution of training hours, technical-tactical actions, volume of technical-tactical actions, effectiveness of technical-tactical actions.

INTRODUCTION.

Sport is what people want to do, public sport is regular employment on the necessary conditions for the development of sports in the country. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Minister of Physical Education and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan” decided (2018-5 March) to execute the citizens of Kanga for not showing interest in sports, regularly playing sports planned employment is the main responsibility of Beb belgilab. In particular, Khotin-Kyzylorda, the development of sports was organized separately in ezgu-Uzbekistan, where children were engaged in the development of the world of kelisha, ulgayishi, upbringing and aging of the nation. Khotin-Kyzylorda sport strengthens health, strengthens the world of kengaitiriba, strengthens the culture of yuksaltirmokda. Family, Jamiyat, Fatherland oldidag, responsible persons teran anglab, soglom and bakhtli turmush kurmokda.

In modern science, in relation to changes in the external environment, internal environment and activities, the features of adaptation processes, that is, adaptation processes carried out in the female body, are not sufficiently studied. So, during the period of women's involvement in heavy sports, there was no scientific basis for reflection on the impact and consequences of the extremely intense specific adaptation processes that they undergo in their organisms on the characteristics of women's performance of ancient natural biological activities. Unlike other sports, ercoclar and ercoclar

organisms have different natural and biological properties, that is, sexual dimorphism is characteristic of certain sports and has an appropriate purpose.

At the same time, as in the case of other sports, sports activities are aimed at improving organizational characteristics, as well as developing, developing and developing businesses, developing youth, developing Celtic origin, and developing opportunities. The stress can be changed as a result of inertial torsion, resulting in deformation, deformation resulting from inertial torsion. Now erkak sportchilarga is in relative adaptation - moslashov hot turli tizimlard has been working for a long time, There is an approach to adapting plastics. It can be weak and weak due to tizimia nervosa or neuromuscular tizimidir. Sport is a competitive round in which there is a lot of stress, a lot of psycho-emotional violence on the part of Olib keladi. At the same time, as in the case of other biological organisms, the influence of the environment on the biologist's body may be insignificant, sometimes ercaclar may be more complex than ercaclar.

During competitions and world Championships and Olympiads, athletes must be ready to compete, but not to compete in this sport. All records set by athletes who competed at the Olympic Games comply with the regulatory requirements for men's sports disciplines. Gymnastics, volleyball, tennis, torches, kurash and basketball sports turlaringan egallagan kyzylarimiz Uzbekistan Asian and Folk Sports Championship was honored to participate. In order to get the desired result, the following steps must be performed: annealing, etc. The causes of movement, respiration, almashin substances under various influences, edlar organisms and parkalanishiga hydrocarbons, protection of the body from possible violations, the development of Karabakh agriculture from inhibition, as a rule, aitgand, fatty deposits of the uzak period, this is the meaning of the life of the Prophet Muhammad, may Allah bless him and greet him. In gymnastics, sports training includes running with a ball and running with a ball, a person trains the body by doing squats, tanning in proportion to height, a person trains with a ball and perfect shape. At the same time, when bone tissue, joints, and internal organs are subjected to loads exceeding the physiological norm, the growth and formation of these organs will not be adversely affected.

According to these characteristics, it is a reasonable sport to recommend to young men and women to engage in gymnastics. Since gymnastics raises the body's adaptation possibilities to a high level, it creates a possibility for the body to contract various diseases, and in case of a disease, to overcome it and recover from it healthy, that is, without complications.

Before performing any physical exercises, the organs and systems of the body must undergo a period of preparation for intense activity.

The main essence of this period is that when starting to perform physical exercises at once, different organs and systems enter the highest level of performance not at the same time, but one after the other, at different time intervals. During preparation for high-level physical exercises, body parts are simultaneously, that is, synchronously, leading to preparation for high-level activity.

After the preparatory period, actions consisting of simple elements are performed, then the structure of the exercises becomes more complex, the pace and rhythm of their execution increases, and all systems of the body demonstrate their readiness to perform high loads, perform high-level activities, and their capabilities.

During the preparatory period, not only the muscles "warm up", but the activity of blood circulation, breathing and other systems gradually increases, which ensures a high level of manifestation of the body's physical capabilities achieved during the period of adaptation.

Due to the positive effect of physical education and sports on the developing body, all organs, systems and the whole organism are increasing the features of adaptation to changes in the internal

and external environment on a wide and deep scale. However, the most important factor of health is the maturity of the adaptive nature of the organism. Children and adolescents growing up in conditions of low mobility (hypokinesia) do not have a satisfactory level of adaptation of the body and organs.

Because of this, their organism cannot adapt in time and adequately to various and sudden changes in the internal environment and activities of the external environment.

As a result, various pathological processes and diseases occur in the children's body. This situation is especially manifested in the growing body of girls who get many diseases during the process of adaptation to pregnancy. On the other hand, the generations born from such women will have weak adaptation characteristics in their later life, and their opportunities to fulfill their main duties in adulthood, including the protection of the state, the nation, their people, and their sacred military duties will be limited. The young generation that regularly engages in physical education will become a healthy pillar of the society in the future and will leave behind a healthy generation.

Popularization of physical education and sports is defined as one of the important directions of social policy in our country. Because sport strengthens the health of the population, by educating the young generation to be healthy and well-rounded, it establishes a healthy way of life in the society. Prevents various diseases, harmful habits among young people. Sport plays an important role in the formation of high culture and patriotism. Achievements in this field will make the country known to the world and will bring pride to all compatriots.

Physical training in sports practice is usually divided into two closely related types of general and special physical training. During life, human health, mental and physical activity, development of sports skills during many years of sports training are primarily related to the content and level of these two types of training.

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